

TEACHERS' CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT COMPETENCE AND LEARNERS' BEHAVIOR IN RURAL AND URBAN AREAS

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Abstract: This study primarily aims to assess the teacher's classroom management competence and learners' behavior in rural and urban areas. It utilized the descriptive-comparative method. The results of the study provided an insight into what classroom management strategies practiced by the teacher has best positive effect on the learner's behavior in the rural and urban classroom settings. Furthermore, it seeks to determine the if the teacher's training and ability has an impact in managing a class of diverse personalities.

The results revealed that the teachers are capable and skilled in dealing with different behaviors of students. Additionally, teachers in the urban and rural areas have been evaluating their management strategies to fit it the student's needs and always practice management strategies such as the learner-centered approach that helps them in improving their student's behavior.

Moreover, the results also show that Students in the urban and rural area had similar set of problematic behaviors but may vary only on the prevalence due to geographical factors, urban students are more vulnerable to bad influences brought about by the many distractions of the city, such as computer gaming shops and other recreations while rural area students can be easily monitored by parents and teachers in and out of the school. Lastly, a teacher's set of capability and skills affects his/her classroom management strategies as well as these strategies affects the learners' behavior in elementary schools in the rural and urban areas.

Keywords: learners' behaviour, classroom management strategies, teacher's training, skills affects.

1. INTRODUCTION

Classroom management is widely viewed by most educators, as the number one concern in schools. From 1967 through 1997 results of researches identified classroom management as the most important problem that teachers face. Some researchers ranked classroom management as the second greatest problem facing schools. Many teachers lack training in the use of effective classroom management strategies (Jackson, 2005).

A primary problem with determining research-based approaches to classroom management is establishing a definition. Classroom management has been defined broadly as any action a teacher takes to create an environment that supports and facilitates both academic and social-emotional learning (Evertson& Weinstein, 2006). Instructional procedures could also be considered classroom management by this definition; however, effective instruction alone is insufficient for establishing universal classroom management. Procedures that structure the classroom environment, encourage

appropriate behavior, and reduce the occurrence of inappropriate behavior are necessary for strong classroom management (Evertson, Emmer, Sanford, & Clements, 1983). Instructional procedures, although equally important to the classroom environment, can be considered a separate set of procedures.

Furthermore, researchers found out that classroom managerial problems can have a substantive impact on the effectiveness of teaching and quality of learning (Hoy, 1990; Marzano, 2003; Schmidt, 1992). While an overabundance of opinions on classroom management are available from which to choose, many teachers remain certain strategies as to what to do when faced with difficulties in classroom situations (Taylor, 1987).

The components of effective classroom management are important in several ways. For example, focusing on preventive rather than reactive procedures establishes a positive classroom environment in which the teacher focuses on students who appropriately behave (Lewis & Sugai, 1999). Rules and routines are powerful preventative components to classroom organization and management plans because they establish a behavioral context for the classroom that includes what is expected, what will be reinforced, and what will be retaught if inappropriate behavior occurs (Colvin et al., 1993). This prevents problem behavior by giving students specific, appropriate behaviors to engage in. Monitoring student behavior allows the teacher to acknowledge students who are engaging in appropriate behavior and prevent misbehavior from escalating (Colvin et al., 1993).

One example of a whole-class classroom management approach is Classroom Organization and Management Program (Evertson et al., 1988). COMP is a professional development series developed by Carolyn Evertson and colleagues (1988) designed to create effective learning environments. The main components of COMP are: (1) organizing the classroom; (2) planning and teaching rules and procedures; (3) managing student work and improving student accountability; (4) maintaining good student behavior; (5) planning and organizing; (6) conducting instruction and maintaining momentum; and (7) getting the year off to a good start.

The ability of the teachers to organize and manage the behavior of their students is critical to achieving positive educational outcomes. Although sound behavior management does not guarantee effective instruction, it establishes the environmental context that makes good instruction possible. Reciprocally, highly effective instruction reduces, but does not eliminate classroom behavior problems (Emmer & Stough, 2001).

In view of the foregoing cycle of student behavioral problems that teachers encounter, arises a question of what is the best classroom management strategy that eliminates or eradicates the occurrence of the problem, hence the researcher took interest to investigate what will be the best solution to create a conducive learning environment that will encourage and motivate students to change their manners and attitudes inside and outside the classroom.

It is undeniably true that teachers always employ classroom management strategies to ensure total control of the behavior of the students, yet the effectivity varies with the kind of learners that the class has. In this study, the researcher aims to know what classroom management strategies practiced by the teacher has best positive effect on the learner's behavior in the rural and urban classroom settings. Furthermore, it seeks to determine if the teacher's training and ability has an impact in managing a class of diverse personalities.

Objectives of the Study

This study primarily aims to assess the teacher's classroom management competence and learners' behavior in rural and urban areas.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following:

1. Find out the profile of the teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 civil status;
 - 1.4 number of years in teaching; and
 - 1.5 training and seminars attended

2. Determine the classroom management competence by the teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 organizing the classroom;
 - 2.2 planning and teaching rules and procedures;
 - 2.3 managing student work and improving student accountability;
 - 2.4 maintaining good student behavior;
 - 2.5 planning and organizing;
 - 2.6 conducting instruction and maintaining momentum; and
 - 2.7 getting the year off to a good start.
3. Determine the learners' behavior in rural and urban areas.
4. Ascertain the significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and their classroom management competence.
5. Ascertain the significant relationship between the teachers' classroom management competence and learners' behavior in rural and urban areas.
6. Elicit feedbacks and experiences from the teachers assigned in rural and urban areas.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the profile of the teachers to their classroom management competence.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the teachers' classroom management competence and learners' behavior in rural and urban areas.

Framework of the Study

The study considered the following theoretical and conceptual frameworks as the main and strong foundations in the due course of the study.

Theoretical framework. Choice Theory was a classroom management theory developed by Dr. William Glasser, that explains that human behavior is based on internal motivation. As Dr. Glasser explains in the most recent of his widely read books, Choice Theory, all our behavior is chosen as we continually attempt to meet one or more of the five basic needs that are part of our genetic structure.

The Glasser Model views the role of teachers as helpers of those in their learning environment. The idea behind it is that all behavior is an issue of choice; teachers should merely serve to facilitate the making of good decisions. Key points: Teachers create environments - and curricula - that cultivate appropriate behavior through meeting learners' needs for belonging and the feeling of empowerment; Classroom rules and their enforcement remain a key factor in making learners responsible for their behavior choices; Discussion, reflection and even making amends are positively encouraged, rather than the administering of simple rewards and punishments. Choice Theory was designed to assist learners in understanding the motivations behind their behavior, so that they might learn to make better choices.

The theory is based on the notion that the classroom environment - and the curriculum - should create a safe place for learning by meeting the needs for freedom, a sense of belonging, a share of power, and the need to have fun. Glasser furthermore stresses we are, in fact, helping learners achieve success by teaching them to make appropriate behavioral choices. According to Glasser, behavior boils down to a matter of personal choice. A learner's behavior stems from their choices; it's the teacher's duty to help the learner make good choices, resulting in first-rate behavior. In this framework, teachers should; stress the importance of learner responsibility; the establishing of rules that lead to success; accept no excuses for inappropriate learner actions; require value judgments from learners; suggest suitable alternatives; bring into play responsible consequences and carry out continual review with the class. The benefits of Choice Theory Glasser believed in providing learners with a choice in deciding not only classroom rules but also in the curriculum itself. This helps the learners take ownership of the learning process, leading to increased enthusiasm, confidence and participation, or so the theory goes.

Conceptual framework. The conceptual framework of this study was developed through the gathered information. The main purpose of the study is to determine the classroom management competence being practiced by the teachers, explore the relationship of classroom management competence and the learner’s behavior in the rural and urban areas.

After the conduct of the study it is expected that teachers will be able to attain healthy and conducive environment that is instrumental in the learning process of students. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents, analyze, and interprets the results the results based on the objectives of the study. The raw data gathered from the respondents on the teacher’s classroom competence and learner’s behavior in urban and rural areas will be presented based on its findings and implications. The data collected are presented in tables including its analysis and interpretation written into narrative form.

Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents

This part of the presentation discusses the socio-demographic profile of the school heads, particularly on age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, number of years in teaching, and trainings and seminars attended.

The table below presents the profile of teacher respondents in the urban and rural areas, which includes the age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, number of years in teaching, and trainings and seminars attended.

Age. The result under the variable profile revealed that out of the 15 teacher respondents in the rural area, there are 9 or 60 percent who are below 30 and are young and 6 or 40 percent are in the middle age ranging from 31-35 years old. On the other hand, among the 15 teachers’ respondents in the urban area 6 or 40 percent are in old age ranging from 49-59 years old, 5 or 33.33 percent are in the middle age with ages ranging from 31-35 years old and 4 or 26.67 are below 30 years old and are categorized as young.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Profile of the Teacher Respondents

	Urban Teachers		Rural Teachers	
	f	%	f	%
Age				
60 above (senior citizen)	0	0.00	0	0.00
45-59 (old age)	6	40.00	0	0.00
31-35 (middle age)	5	33.33	6	40.00
30 below (young)	4	26.67	9	60.00
Total	15	100	15	100
Sex				
Male	0	0.00	1	6.67
Female	15	100	14	93.33
Total	15	100	15	100
Civil Status				
Single	2	13.33	5	33.33
Married	13	86.87	10	66.67
Widow	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	15	100	15	100
Educational Attainment				
Doctorate Degree Holder	0	0.00	0	0.00
MA with Doctoral Units	0	0.00	0	0.00
Master’s Degree Holder	0	0.00	1	6.67
BS with Masteral Units	9	60.00	9	60.00
BS Degree Holder	6	40.00	5	33.33
Total	15	100	15	100
Number of years in teaching				
21 years and above	6	40.00	0	0.00
16 – 20 years	2	13.33	0	0.00
11 – 15 years	0	0.00	0	0.00
6 – 10 years	4	26.67	2	13.33
1 – 5 years	3	20.00	8	53.34
1 year and below	0	0.00	5	33.33
Total	15	100	15	100
Training and seminars attended				
International level	0	0.00	0	0.00
National level	0	0.00	0	0.00
Regional level	1	6.67	0	0.00
District/Local level	14	93.33	15	100
Total	15	100	15	100

Sex. The table shows that majority of the respondents in the urban areas are all or 100 percent are female while in the rural areas, 14 or 93.33 percent are female and 1 or 6.67 percent are male. This clearly means that in both urban and rural settings, female teachers are more dominant in numbers.

Civil Status. Among the 15 respondents in the urban area, 13 or 86.37 percent are married and 2 or 13.33 percent are single. In the rural area, 10 or 66.67 percent are married and 5 or 33.33 percent are single. The result from both urban and rural areas revealed that majority of the respondents are married and has families.

Educational Attainment. Under this variable, 9 or 60 percent of the respondents from the urban area are bachelor’s degree holders with master’s units and 6 or 40 percent are bachelor’s degree holder. Among the 15 respondents in the rural areas, 9 or 60 percent are bachelor’s degree holder with master’s units, 5 or 33.33 percent are bachelor’s degree holder and 1 or 6.67 percent are master’s degree holder.

Number of Years in Teaching. The table above reveals that among the respondents in the urban area, 6 or 40 percent has been in the service for 21 years and above, 4 or 26.67 percent are in the service for 6-10 years, 3 or 20 percent has been teaching for 1-5 years and 2 or 13.33 percent has been in the teaching profession for 16-20 years in service. While in the rural areas, the results showed that 8 or 53.34 percent are in teaching 1-5 years, 5 or 33.33 percent has served as a teacher below 1 year and 2 or 13.33 percent has been teaching for 6-10 years.

Trainings and Seminars Attended. Among the 15 respondents in the urban area, 14 or 93.33 percent had attended trainings in the district/local level only and 1 or 6.67 had been to regional trainings. In the rural area, 15 or 100 percent of all the respondents had only attended district/local level of trainings and seminars.

Classroom Management Competence of the Teachers

Teachers’ classroom management competence was determined in terms of: organizing the classroom; planning and teaching rules and procedures; managing student work and improving student accountability; maintaining good student behavior; planning and organizing; conducting instruction and maintaining momentum; and getting the year off to a good start.

Table 2 presents the discussion of the result of the variables in managing classroom behavior. As shown in the table, in the urban area schools, the teacher respondents gave the highest mean of 4.87 to the statement, conduct orientation on classroom rules, policies and regulations, its sanctions and penalties in case of violations committed by the students. Likewise, in the rural areas, it garnered a 5.00 mean that implies in both settings, teachers are fully competent in managing their classes.

On the other hand, a lower mean of 4.33 was given by the respondents to the statement, conduct student behavioral assessment and monitoring on my students which implies teacher are fully competent in the assessment and monitoring of student’s behavior. While another lower mean of 4.60 was given by the teachers in the rural area in the statement, conduct personal counselling in private and address the problem in a calm and respectful way that means teachers should talk to students discreetly to know their problems. This implies teachers are fully competent in conducting counselling to solve problems of students immediately.

Table 2: Classroom Management Competence of the Teachers In Terms of Organizing the Classroom

Indicators	Urban		Rural	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Conduct student behavioral assessment and monitoring on my students.	4.33	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
2. Conduct orientation on classroom rules, policies and regulations, its sanctions and penalties in case of violations committed by the students.	4.87	Fully Competent	5.00	Fully Competent
3. Maintain a record of students who are identified as disruptive to monitor their progress.	4.27	Fully Competent	4.67	Fully Competent

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4. Conduct personal counselling in private and address the problem in a calm and respectful way.	4.53	Fully Competent	4.60	Fully Competent
5. Encourage students to act appropriately and stop misbehaving inside and outside the classroom.	4.60	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
AWM	4.52	Fully Competent	4.76	Fully Competent

All the response in Table 2 in the urban areas garnered a total mean of 4.52 and in the rural areas summed up to 4.76 which indicates that all the teacher is fully competent in managing classroom behavior through activities. This implies a good performance of the teachers in conducting the management and monitoring of their student’s behavior inside their respective classrooms.

Table 3: Classroom Management Competence of the Teachers in Terms of Planning and Teaching Rules and Procedures

Indicators	Urban		Rural	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Coach positive social behaviors (helping, sharing, waiting)	4.80	Fully Competent	4.87	Fully Competent
2. Describe or comment on bad behavior	4.67	Fully Competent	4.67	Fully Competent
3. Reward targeted positive behaviors with incentives (e.g., stickers)	4.47	Fully Competent	4.47	Fully Competent
4. Praise positive behavior	4.87	Fully Competent	4.93	Fully Competent
5. Use Time Out (Time Away to calm down) for aggressive behavior	4.93	Fully Competent	4.93	Fully Competent
6. Single out a child or a group of children for misbehavior	4.47	Fully Competent	4.47	Fully Competent
7. Use physical restraint	1.00	Not Competent	1.00	Not Competent
8. Reprimand in a loud voice	4.40	Fully Competent	4.40	Fully Competent
9. In-house suspension (send to Principal’s office for misbehavior)	4.73	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
10. Warn or threaten to send child out of classroom if s/he doesn’t behave	4.13	Highly Competent	4.13	Highly Competent
11. Send child home for aggressive or destructive misbehavior	4.07	Highly Competent	4.07	Highly Competent
12. Call parents to report bad behavior	4.07	Highly Competent	4.07	Highly Competent
13. Ignore misbehavior that is non-disruptive to class	1.33	Not Competent	1.13	Not Competent
14. Use verbal redirection for child who is disengaged	4.80	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
15. Use problem-solving strategy (e.g., define problem, brainstorm solutions)	4.40	Fully Competent	4.67	Fully Competent
16. Use anger management strategy for self (e.g., deep breaths, positive self-talk)	4.87	Fully Competent	4.87	Fully Competent
17. Prepare children for transitions with predictable routine	4.20	Highly Competent	4.20	Highly Competent
18. Use group incentives	4.73	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
19. Use special privileges (e.g., special helper, extra computer time)	4.93	Fully Competent	4.93	Fully Competent
20. Set up individual incentive program (e.g., stickers, prizes)	4.80	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
21. Give clear positive directions	4.67	Fully Competent	4.67	Fully Competent

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22. Warn of consequences for misbehavior (e.g., loss of privileges)	4.73	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
23. Use clear classroom discipline plan and hierarchy	4.93	Fully Competent	4.93	Fully Competent
24. Use emotion coaching	4.87	Fully Competent	4.87	Fully Competent
25. Use nonverbal signals to redirect child who is disengaged	4.60	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
26. Use persistence coaching (focusing, being patient, working hard)	4.80	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
27. Send home notes (or frowny faces) to report problem behavior to parent	1.00	Not Competent	1.00	Not Competent
28. Send notes/happy grams home about positive behavior	4.07	Highly Competent	4.07	Highly Competent
29. Call child after a bad day	4.20	Highly Competent	4.27	Fully Competent
30. Take a student interest survey	4.93	Fully Competent	4.93	Fully Competent
31. Call parents to report good behavior	4.33	Fully Competent	4.33	Fully Competent
32. Model self-regulation strategies for students	4.47	Fully Competent	4.47	Fully Competent
33. Teach specific social skills in circle time	4.73	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
34. Use imaginary play/drama, stories and puppets to teach problem solving	4.13	Highly Competent	4.13	Highly Competent
35. Set up problem solving scenarios to practice prosocial solutions	4.40	Fully Competent	4.40	Fully Competent
36. Promote respect for cultural differences in my classroom	4.73	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
37. Teach children to ignore disruptive behavior	1.13	Not Competent	1.00	Not Competent
38. Teach children anger management strategies (Turtle technique, calm down thermometer)	4.80	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
AWM	4.22	Fully Competent	4.22	Fully Competent

Table 3 reveals the response of the teacher respondents in the planning and teaching rules and procedures in effecting behavioral change among students. In the urban areas, the teacher respondents gave a highest mean of 4.93 on the following indicators: a. use time out (time away to calm down) for aggressive behavior which implies very often this teaching strategy is useful in managing students who misbehave in class; b. use special privileges (e.g., special helper, extra computer time) which means very often giving special privileges helps a lot in making students behave well in class; c. use clear classroom discipline plan and hierarchy which implies that fully competent teachers must set perimeters pertaining discipline in order for the students to know what are the offenses that will require discipline sanctions; and take a student interest survey which indicates that in knowing what the students interests are, fully competent teachers can formulate interesting activities that will motivate them to behave well in class.

In contrast with the above response, the following indicators garnered the lowest mean of 1.0: a. use physical restraint which means that teachers find it rarely never useful to use physical force in dealing with students who misbehave, it will only result in violent reaction and chaos in the classroom; b. send home notes (or frowny faces) to report problem behavior to parent which implies that solving the problem through first hand intervention would be more appropriate than reporting it immediately to parents that might trigger another problem if parent will react differently and would emotionally upset their child on the process hence it is rarely never useful not to talk to the student first before reporting it to parent if behavior remained incorrigible and hard to manage.

In the rural areas, the teachers rated a highest mean of 4.93 the following indicators: a. praise positive behavior that clearly means verbally telling the students of their good manners and attitude in class motivates them to maintain their status; b. use time out (time away to calm down) for aggressive behavior which implies having a time out is a useful technique to cool down aggressive behavior of students in class; c. take a student interest survey which means that by learning what interest the students has, the teacher could find activities that conform with their interest and are useful in altering attitudes and behavior to make them better in class.

Meanwhile, the rural area teachers ruled that the following mean were not useful by giving the lowest mean of 1.0: a. use physical restraint which explains that using brute force will only encourage students to be violently aggressive because they will feel being provoked into a fight hence it is not useful to resort to it unless there is a threat to the life of other students; b. send home notes (or frowny faces) to report problem behavior to parent that means talking to the student first to find solutions is much appropriate rather than relying on parents to do the tasks because some of them can either be tolerant or demeaning therefore it is not useful to immediately report without giving the student a warning; b. teach children to ignore disruptive behavior which implies that ignoring children was not useful in the premise that the more you ignore the more they misbehave to get your attention.

All the response in the urban areas garnered a total mean of 4.22 that means all the indicators are useful teaching strategies in the management of behavior of students in the class. While a similar mean of 4.22 totaled all the response of the teachers in the rural areas that means that the teaching techniques are useful in managing classroom behavior. It implies that teachers in the urban and rural areas are fully competent in employing behavioral strategies.

Table 4 revealed the perception of the teachers in classroom management employed in terms of managing student work and improving student accountability. The teachers in the urban area showed that they are fully competent to the given statement, involve students in creating classroom norms and rules that they will be expected to follow by giving it a highest mean of 4.93 that means students are given a role in the formulation of the rules and norms that should be observed to follow. This implies that teachers are giving a chance to students to participate in drafting and making the classroom rules because they believe they are more likely to follow it because the made it.

Table 4: Classroom Management Competence of the Teachers in Terms of Managing Student Work and Improving Student Accountability

Indicators	Urban		Rural	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Create a positive atmosphere by greeting students upon entering the classroom.	4.67	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
2. Allow students to take the lead by planning their own academic success.	4.60	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
3. Get students invested in themselves and their work through looking at their daily commitment to their schoolwork by grading themselves.	4.47	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
4. Keep an achievement chart inside the classroom	4.87	Fully Competent	4.87	Fully Competent
5. Involve students in creating classroom norms and rules that they will be expected to follow.	4.93	Fully Competent	5.00	Fully Competent
AWM	4.71	Fully Competent	4.84	Fully Competent

On the other hand, in the rural area, a highest mean of 5.00 was given to the same statement above, that means teachers in the rural area strongly agreed to provide an opportunity for students to draft rules that they deemed appropriate for them. This implies that the teachers have fairly considered the role of the student in following the rules they set because lawmakers are not supposed to be rule breakers.

Meanwhile, a lower mean of 4.47 was given by the urban area teachers to the statement, themselves and their work through looking at their daily commitment to their schoolwork by grading themselves that means teachers fully competent to permit students to evaluate their own performance to monitor their own progress. This implies the teachers allowed students to realize what went wrong and what was right in their own school work, it also promotes building trust between the student and teacher that will encourage students not to cheat on their evaluation for them to see their weaknesses and work on it to improve.

In the rural area, the teachers strongly agreed that students must take the lead by planning their own academic success by giving a lower mean of 4.73 that means they encourage students to set their future plan because it will motivate them to

achieve it. This implies that teachers had given students a chance to set their goals and have dreams that will drive them to work hard in order to achieve it.

An overall mean of 4.71 sums up all the perception of teachers in the urban area which implies that they are fully competent to conduct the activities stated in table 4. Likewise, a total overall mean of 4.54 was derived from all the indicators that means they strongly agreed on the statements presented in the table. This implies that teachers have been conducting the activities to manage the good behavior of students as well as encourage student accountability.

Table 5: Classroom Management Competence of the Teachers in Terms of Maintaining Good Behavior

Indicators	Urban		Rural	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Establish the rules and stick to them.	4.60	Fully Competent	4.67	Fully Competent
2. Make sure students understand the rules and the consequences.	4.53	Fully Competent	4.60	Fully Competent
3. Show interest in all the students. Each one needs to be treated as an individual and with respect, not just another student.	4.73	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
4. Fair and consistent in dealing with students and imposing rules.	4.67	Fully Competent	4.67	Fully Competent
5. Do not humiliate. It creates psychological damage.	4.87	Fully Competent	5.00	Fully Competent
6. Get to know the students, learn their names and use it in and out of class.	4.87	Fully Competent	4.60	Fully Competent
7. Praise good work.	4.80	Fully Competent	4.47	Fully Competent
8. Keep your classroom orderly.	4.40	Fully Competent	4.87	Fully Competent
9. Let your students know you care. Show interest in what student say, whether it pertains directly to the lesson or not.	4.93	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
AWM	4.24	Fully Competent	4.24	Fully Competent

Table 5 presents the perception of teachers on the classroom management strategies employed in terms of maintaining good behavior. The teachers in the urban area strongly agreed on the statement, let your students know you care, show interest in what student say, whether it pertains directly to the lesson or not by giving a highest mean of 4.93 that means teachers are supposed to be the second parents of the students outside their homes thus caring for them makes them at home. This implies that fully competent teachers must consider individual differences and experiences to deeply understand the meaning of their actions and show their affection to the by giving attention to what they say and will have to say.

While in the rural area, the statement, do not humiliate. It creates psychological damage, garnered the highest mean of 5.00 which means teachers must be careful not to put students to shame because it will leave a scar in their hearts and minds. This implies that teachers should always act like family, never to subject any student to humiliation because it might trigger some psychological imbalance that will render the student violent or withdrawn.

On the other hand, a lower mean of 4.40 was strongly agreed by the urban area teachers to the statement, keep your classroom orderly that mean it should be arrange and neatly kept creating a conducive learning facility. This implies that classrooms should not just be clean but as well as arranged according to accessibility to learning, a healthy learning environment is a result of an orderly classroom. Moreover, the rural area teachers agreed that teachers should praise good work of students by giving it a lower mean of 4.47 that means praising for good work will lift the spirit of students and motivate them to do better or maintain their performance. This implies that students should be properly complimented for a job well-done because it will encourage them more to do good and will fuel their desire to maintain their performance to continually receive the praise from teachers.

The perception of teachers in the urban area and rural area both has garnered a total mean of 4.24 which means they are fully competent in the conduct the activities presented in table 5 that implies maintaining good behavior need more than just teaching but also personal involvement to students and being concern of their intellectual and emotional well-being.

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Table 6 reveals the results of the variables under planning and support. Among all the indicators, the statement, review my discipline hierarchy according to the student's developmental ability gained the highest mean of 5.00 which means that once a week the teacher respondents review their discipline strategies in accordance to student's behavioral improvement to ensure that the imposed classroom discipline policy would fit to the level of behavior of the students. This implies that reviewing their strategies would provide them room for improvement on their present strategies employed. Likewise, the statement, manage my stress level utilizing positive cognitive strategies has the same highest mean of 5.0 that means teachers usually suffer bouts of work-related stress that needed control. These implied teachers must manage their stress level once a week to de-load the burden felt in dealing with students with discipline problem in order to balance health and work.

Table 6: Classroom Management Competence of the Teachers in Terms of Planning and Organizing

Indicators	Urban		Rural	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Use self-reflective inventories to plan personal teaching goals	4.80	Once a week	4.93	Once a week
2. Review my progress in reaching goals for individual student behavior plans	4.87	Once a week	4.87	Once a month
3. Review my discipline hierarchy according to the student's developmental ability	5.00	Once a week	4.20	Once a month
4. Collaborate with other teachers for solutions and support	4.73	Once a week	4.07	Once a month
5. Give support to other teachers	3.60	2-3 times per year	2.00	1 time per year
6. Read the classroom management book	4.07	Once a month	3.13	1 time per year
7. Manage my stress level utilizing positive cognitive strategies	5.00	Once a week	2.33	1 time per year
8. Encourage a positive school community (e.g., including input from teacher aides,	1.33	1 time per year	1.67	1 time per year
9. sharing successes in the classroom with the principal)	3.53	2-3 times per year	3.07	1 time per year
AWM	3.69	2-3 times per year	3.03	2-3 times per year

Meanwhile, a lowest mean of 1.33 was given in the indicator, encourage a positive school community (e.g., including input from teacher aides) which attests that though teachers may want a happy learning environment, activities that will encourage good camaraderie and relationship happens only 1 time per year thus goals of a positive school community cannot be fully achieved.

In the rural area, the statement, use self-reflective inventories to plan personal teaching goals garnered the highest mean of 4.93 that means teachers are doing once a week self-evaluation to further create much effective teaching strategies that will meet personal teaching goals, While, the lowest mean of 1.67 was given to the statement, encourage a positive school community (e.g., including input from teacher aides) this indicates that inasmuch as teachers wanted to build a positive school environment, this cannot be materialized because it is done 1 time per year only. This implies that more emphasis will be given to creating a positive school community through integrating values formation in each subject and teaching aides.

All indicators in the urban area has gained a total mean of 3.69 which validates that planning and support activities by teachers are done 2-3 times per year that displayed the concern of teachers in doing their best to improve their performance in managing their classroom and turning it into a conducive knowledge providing venue. In the rural area, all the indicators have gained a total mean of 3.03 which means the activities under planning and organizing are done by teachers 1 time per year. This implies that teachers in the rural area have manageable behavioral problems that never required them to frequently conduct the activities stated under planning and organizing. This may have been attributed to the type of environment students has that contributed to their behavior.

The table below revealed the results of the perception of teachers in classroom management strategies employed in terms of conducting instruction and maintaining momentum.

Table 7: Classroom Management Competence of the Teachers in Terms of Conducting Instruction and Maintaining Momentum

Indicators	Urban		Rural	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Opening the period-helping the student transition, set tone for the day.	4.47	Fully Competent	4.40	Fully Competent
2. Checking classwork or homework, let the student check their own work or checked by their peers and collected for follow-up.	4.67	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
3. Recitation-check for student understanding of recent content.	4.80	Fully Competent	4.60	Fully Competent
4. Content development. Presents new information, demonstrate ideas, elaborate on concepts, allow questions to maintain student involvement.	4.73	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
5. Discussion. Teacher-led discussions that encourage students to discuss recent events, topics or results.	4.40	Fully Competent	4.33	Fully Competent
6. Seatwork. Can be done individually or cooperatively.	4.87	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
7. Small group work-cooperative learning.	4.60	Fully Competent	4.53	Fully Competent
8. Test Administration-quizzes, test to determine student's progress.	4.60	Fully Competent	4.73	Fully Competent
9. Student demonstration and presentation.	4.33	Fully Competent	4.27	Fully Competent
10. Bring the classroom end in an orderly manner.	4.67	Fully Competent	4.40	Fully Competent
AWM	4.61	Fully Competent	4.56	Fully Competent

Of all the indicators, the statement, recitation-check for student understanding of recent content gained the highest mean of 4.80 that mean the teachers in the urban area agreed that recitations are one of the best strategies in finding out if students have understood their lessons. It implies that assessment of student learning though verbal recount is effective in knowing if students really has absorbed the knowledge given. Likewise, same 4.80 mean was afforded by the rural area teachers to the following statements: a. checking classwork or homework, let the student check their own work or checked by their peers and collected for follow-up; b. content development. Presents new information, demonstrate ideas, elaborate on concepts, allow questions to maintain student involvement. This mean that teachers in the rural area has agreed in letting students check their own classwork and homework that implies they are promoting honesty among students in evaluating their own classwork and homework, that will provide teachers to know who among their students had been honest by not tampering their work just to be on top. Another thing is, teachers in the rural area agreed that in sharing content to their students' questions can be raised along the way for further understanding. This implies that they gave opportunity to students to make clarifications and follow-up queries to completely absorb and retain the lessons given.

On the other hand, a lower mean of 4.33 was given to the statement, student demonstration and presentation that means that teachers in the urban area affirmed that students must conduct activities such as reporting, presentations and discussion to enhance their communication skills. This implies that teachers in the urban area has promoted a student-centered learning wherein teachers are just the facilitators. While in the rural area, teachers strongly agreed to give a 4.27 mean to same statement that means they let their students do demonstrations and content sharing as part of their daily instruction activities. This implies that teachers in the rural area are fully competent in adopting the student-centered learning where they train students to do teacher's work not for their convenience but to develop their communication skills and to discover their own strength and confidence in sharing knowledge to their fellow classmates.

An overall mean of 4.61 was garnered on the perception of teachers on conducting instruction and maintaining momentum which means that they have done the processes in providing their students the knowledge they need in a different and student involved perspective. This implies that outcomes-based education is now the new trend in learning. On the part of the rural area teachers, a total mean of 4.56 sums up all their perceptions that indicated they conform on the instruction process stated on the table. This implies that fully competent teachers in the rural area has embraced student-centered learning as part of the holistic development of their student by encouraging them to become knowledge providers of their own.

Table 8 revealed the results of the perception of teachers in the classroom management employed in getting the year off with a good start. The urban area teachers strongly agreed that by speaking courteously and calmly, “please”, “thank you” “excuse me” courtesies are to be expected by giving the highest mean of 4.93 which means they concur that by being courteous in the start of the class, students will also be returning the favor.

Table 8: Classroom Management Competence of the Teachers in Terms of Getting the Year Off to a Good Start

Indicators	Urban		Rural	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Create a positive climate in your classroom.	4.87	Fully Competent	4.80	Fully Competent
2. Speak courteously and calmly say “please”, “thank you” “excuse me” for courtesies to become expected.	4.93	Fully Competent	4.87	Fully Competent
3. Share information-learn names as soon as possible. Speak personally with students to get to know them as individuals.	4.67	Fully Competent	4.60	Fully Competent
4. Establish a feeling of community. Teach students to work cooperatively and give them regular opportunities to learn in structured cooperative activities.	4.73	Fully Competent	4.53	Fully Competent
5. Introductions, room description, get-acquainted activities, time fillers, administrative activities (distributing textbooks, etc.)	4.80	Fully Competent	4.47	Fully Competent
AWM	4.80	Fully Competent	4.65	Fully Competent

This implies that courtesies are a way of creating a good impression among the students and it also relive the values of respect that slowly students have forgotten in the onset of modern era in technology. Another high mean of 4.80 was given to the statement, create a positive climate in your classroom was a necessity by the rural area teachers which means they prepared to set a positive environment to their students through warm welcome activities and acceptance. This implies that setting positive climate is a priority for teachers in order to let their students be comfortable in their seats and have a harmonious relationship with their classmates.

Relatively, a lower mean of 4.67 was given to the statement, share information-learn names as soon as possible, speak personally with students to get to know them as individuals by the urban area teachers that means they affirmed they must have an exchange of personal information with their students for the latter to know them to make them comfortable in class. This implies that sharing of personal information of teachers will make students share their own personal information too and first name basis is a way of letting them know they are all important and significant. While another lower mean of 4.47 was given to the statement, introductions, room description, get-acquainted activities, time fillers, administrative activities (distributing textbooks, etc.) by the rural area teachers that means they are into giving time to make students at home in their school. This implies that students always must feel comfortable and at home in their classrooms and activities during first day of class matters in motivating students to come to class every day.

All the indicators in the urban area garnered a total mean of 4.80 that means all the activities and strategies stated in table 8 agreed by the teachers as part of starting a good year off. This implies that teachers must create the best impression in

the start of class that will be lasting to the students thus giving them the drive to come to class daily. While in the rural area, the teachers also agreed all the indicators stated above by garnering a total mean of 4.65 that means teachers in the rural area always start their year off with a warm welcome by making their classrooms a venue for healthy learning.

Learner’s Behavior in Rural and Urban Areas

The table below shows the results of the teacher’s perception on the learner’s behavior in urban and rural areas. In the urban area, the teachers strongly agreed on the following indicators by giving the highest mean of 5.0: excessive noise, obscene language/gesture, sexual harassment, theft that means these behaviors are present in their school and has identified as problematic behaviors.

This implies that in urban area, where students are exposed many activities that influences their behaviors, problematic characteristics emerge thus giving teachers hard time in performing their duties and responsibilities. Likewise, in the rural area, teachers strongly agreed that the set of behaviors in the indicator are manifested in some of their students thus giving the highest mean of 5.0 to the following: fighting, excessive noise, abusive language, obscene language/gesture, sexual harassment, and theft that simply means these negative behaviors are still present even in the rural area.

Table 9: Learners Behavior in Rural and Urban Areas

Indicators	Urban		Rural	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Disobedience	4.93	Strongly Agree	4.73	Strongly Agree
2. Classroom interference	4.27	Strongly Agree	4.53	Strongly Agree
3. Disrespect	4.87	Strongly Agree	4.93	Strongly Agree
4. Fighting	4.93	Strongly Agree	5.00	Strongly Agree
5. Excessive Noise	5.00	Strongly Agree	5.00	Strongly Agree
6. Abusive language	4.40	Strongly Agree	5.00	Strongly Agree
7. Throwing things on the floor	4.27	Strongly Agree	4.07	Agree
8. Obscene Language/Gesture	5.00	Strongly Agree	5.00	Strongly Agree
9. Tardiness	4.27	Strongly Agree	4.20	Strongly Agree
10. Sexual harassment	5.00	Strongly Agree	5.00	Strongly Agree
11. Repeated disruption of classes	4.73	Strongly Agree	4.27	Strongly Agree
12. Theft	5.00	Strongly Agree	5.00	Strongly Agree
AWM	4.72	Strongly Agree	4.73	Strongly Agree

Additionally, this also implies that despite of the remoteness of rural area schools, unruly behaviors still thrive due to the influence of media, social media and other modern communication devices that allow children to see violence, aggression and emulate them.

Relationship of Variables

This section presents the significant relationships between different variables as shown in the succeeding tables.

Table 10: Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Teachers and their Classroom Management of Competence in Urban and Rural Areas

Variable	Urban			Rural		
	t-value	Sig.	Decision	t-value	Sig.	Decision
Age	-.497	.653	Ho Accepted	.217	.848	Ho Accepted
Sex	.409.554	.753	Ho Accepted	-3.183	.051	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	-.635	.678	Ho Accepted	1.087	.474	Ho Accepted
Highest educational qualification	-.637	.559	Ho Accepted	.632	.562	Ho Accepted
Number of years	1.225	.288	Ho Accepted	.708	.518	Ho Accepted
Training and seminars	-.183	.859	Ho Accepted	-.199	.853	Ho Accepted

Table 10 presents the result of the t-test that showed that there is enough evidence to support the claim that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and their classroom management strategies in urban and rural areas.

Table 11: Significant Relationship between the Classroom Management Strategies Employed by the Teachers and Learner's Behavior in Rural and Urban Areas

Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
Organizing the Classroom	.614	.195	Ho Accepted
Planning and Teaching Rules and Procedure	.999**	.000	Ho Rejected
Managing Student Work and Improving Student Accountability	.812	.095	Ho Accepted
Maintaining Good Student Behavior	-.046	.906	Ho Accepted
Planning and Organizing	.696*	.037	Ho Rejected
Conducting Instruction and Maintaining Momentum	.757*	.011	Ho Rejected
Getting the Year off to a Good Start	.746	.148	Ho Accepted

Table 11 presents the result of the t-test that showed that there is enough evidence to support the claim that there is no significant difference between the classroom management competence employed by the teachers and learners' behavior in rural and urban areas.

3. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the followings conclusions were drawn:

The teacher respondents of the study evidently shown that most of them are experienced educators based on their years of service, has acquired master units to upgrade their intellectual capabilities and been trained in the district/local level. This implies that all of them are capable and skilled in dealing with different behaviors of students.

The classroom management competence of teachers in organizing the classroom, teachers had been practicing the activities that leads to creating a healthy learning environment. Teaching rules and procedures had provided an avenue for teachers to achieve their goals in building positive relationships and conducive classroom ambiance. Teachers in the urban and rural areas had been evaluating their management strategies to fit it to the student's needs.

As to the classroom management strategies employed by teachers in urban and rural areas, they always practice the management activities that helps them in improving their student's behavior. The teaching rules and procedure are conducted to enable teachers achieve their goals of providing students a healthy learning environment through maintaining the good behavior of their students.

Teachers had adopted the learner-centered approach in conducting their instructions and maintaining the momentum. It significantly improves the behavior of student's behavior due to their engagement in classwork. Establishing a positive classroom climate during class opening or first day of class will motivate student to attend class regularly. It was found out that a teacher's capability and skills affect his/her classroom management strategies as well as these strategies affects the learner's behavior in elementary schools in the rural and urban areas.

Students in the urban and rural area had similar set of problematic behaviors but may vary only on the prevalence due to geographical factors, urban students are more vulnerable to bad influences brought about by the many distractions of the city, such as computer gaming shops and other recreations while rural area students can be easily monitored by parents and teachers in and out of the school. Lastly, a teacher's set of capability and skills affects his/her classroom management strategies as well as these strategies affects the learner's behavior in elementary schools in the rural and urban areas.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. Teachers in both urban and rural areas should be sent to trainings to gain more knowledge in creating a positive classroom setting, structural designs that will motivate student to attend class daily.
2. Teachers should have a behavioral plan that is set to monitor progress and improvement of students with problematic behaviors.
3. Teacher student workshops and teambuilding should be initiated to establish a good relationship between student and teachers.

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4. Teacher performance evaluation should include classroom management observations to assess if existing strategies still work or not, or there is a need to plan new ways to ensure the maintenance of good behavior of students inside and outside the classroom.
5. Teacher-parent workshops should be done to further strengthen the relationship and to set an agreement of where teacher and parents intervention start and where it ends, to avoid overlapping of functions in dealing with students and their children.
6. Teacher-parent-student conference should be frequently done if students behavior does not improve despite of numerous interventions done by the teacher.

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